

COMPARISON OF STRUCTURAL, SURFACE HARDNESS, CORROSION RESISTANCE AND INTERFACIAL CONTACT RESISTANCE PROPERTIES OF AISI 304, 310 AND 316 STAINLESS STEEL

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Abstract:

Surface modification of Stainless Steel (SS) is carried out by nitriding for three different types of SS namely AISI 304, 310 and 316 and different properties is compared. It is also compared after TiN coating. After nitriding and coating, surface were characterized by various techniques. Structural characterization were carried out using SEM, compound formation were determined using XRD, corrosion resistance were carried out using Electrochemical method and interfacial contact resistance were measured. Improvement in these properties is described and compared.

Key Words: Stainless Steel, Surface Hardness, Corrosion Resistance & Interfacial Contact Resistance

Introduction:

Importance of stainless steel is well known to human beings. Due to its wide applications in industries as well as domestic appliances, it is imperative to modify its surface properties. Surface properties can be modified by coating, ion implantation, nitriding at high temperature and plasma nitriding [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6].

The present research work has been undertaken in view of developing a duplex coating structure on the surface of the steel to meet the requirement of the bipolar plates for the fuel cell applications. The coating was analyzed with an emphasis on their structural characterization and studies of surface hardness, corrosion and conductivity properties. The aim of the work is twofold, one from the applied point of view and the other from fundamental aspects. In application part, the main objective is to develop a good coating material with good surface properties, whereas in the fundamental part, the motive is to understand the structural, hardness and surface conductivity properties of three different austenitic stainless steels 304, 310 and 316 grades.

Experimental:

In the present research work, three different grades of ASS (Austenitic Stainless Steels), i.e. AISI 304, 310 and 316 were selected for the sample materials. In brief, these steels have major constituents are Chromium (Cr) and Iron (Fe) whereas the minor constituents are Molybdenum (Mo), Silicon (Si), Manganese (Mn), Nickel (Ni), Carbon (C), Sulphur (S) and Phosphorus (P). The distributions of these constituents in these steels are given in Table 1.

The commercial grade of above mentioned austenitic steels in the shape of sheet of 1.5 mm thickness were procured for the specimens/samples preparation. The sheets were sectioned into a square shape of 10×10 mm size specimens. The specimens used for sample were prepared by metallographic standard procedure i.e. polished with SiC paper of #80 up to #1200 grit pasted on wheel running at 540 rpm. The final surface finish was done using 1µm diamond paste. The diamond polish produced the mirror like finish on the surface of the samples. The polished specimens were washed with acetone and dried at room temperature prior to nitriding.

Table 1: Major constituents of AISI 304, AISI 310 and AISI 316

Samples	Cr	Ni	Mn	Si	C	S	P	Fe
AISI 304	18.9	9.2	2.0	0.8	0.05	0.02	0.03	Balance
AISI 310	24.4	20.1	1.91	1.60	0.075	0.023	0.045	Balance
AISI 316	16-18	10-14	1.7	0.8	0.03	0.03	0.04	Balance

In the present investigation, the glow discharge plasma nitriding process was carried out in an automated bell shaped stainless steel vacuum chamber as described in our previous papers [5,6]. The nitriding was done on three variable temperatures, i.e., 400°C, 450°C and 500°C. A thin layer of the Titanium Nitride (TiN) nanoparticles was deposited on plasma nitrided AISI 304, 310 and 316 stainless steel samples using reactive RF magnetron sputtering process. The plasma nitriding was done at 400°C, 450°C and 500°C.

The X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) measurements of the untreated, plasma nitrided and TiN coated AISI 304, 310 and 316 austenitic stainless steel were carried out. X-ray diffractometer (Bruker D 8 Advance x-ray diffractometer) were used. By using a filtered monochromatic radiation of CuK_α of wavelength $\lambda = 0.15406$ nm through a Ni filter, the diffraction data were recorded. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) made JEOL made model JSM-6390 LV (as given in Fig. 2.4) was used to more precise examination of the nitride layer thickness and their microstructure alteration nearby the interfacial region. For these analysis, the untreated, plasma nitrided and TiN coated samples were cut into cross-sectional. The potentiodynamic test was conducted with CH instrument, USA, model 680B electrochemical workstation equipped with CHI660B software controlled by a computer in a three electrode setup. Sample work as a working electrode, platinum mesh as counter electrode, submerged in a 0.5 M H_2SO_4 electrolyte in a stimulated environment by conventional three electrode system. The reference electrode, Ag/AgCl at 0.64 V vs SHE, was connected to the electrolyte compartment by a salt bridge. The electrolyte was heated 80°C and bubbled with nitrogen gas for 20 min to reduce the concentration of dissolved oxygen prior to the introduction of the AISI 304 steel sample. The Interfacial Contact Resistance (ICR) measurements of the untreated and surface modified steel samples were conducted before and after potentiostatic test in the simulated fuel cell environment by the method described by Wang et al. [7]. The detailed process is described in our papers [5, 6].

Results and Discussion:

Fig. 1 shows the XRD plot of AISI 304 SS at different temperatures. Fig. 2 shows the XRD of TiN coated samples nitrided at (a) 400°C (b) 450°C and (c) 500°C. Untreated AISI 310 and 316 austenitic stainless steel samples diffraction patterns shows only the characteristic γ -Fe (austenite) or γ -phase whereas the AISI 304 steel shows both γ -Fe (austenite) or γ -phase and α -Fe (ferrite) phase. For all steel samples, the plasma nitriding at 400 and 450°C shows the expanded austenite phase (S-phase or γ_s -phase). With increasing the treatment temperature, more shifting and broadening in the γ -phase peaks were observed towards lower diffraction angles. The plasma nitriding at 500°C also shows the CrN phase formation. It is due to the segregation of Cr at the top layer of the steel at high temperature, thus, forms CrN phase in presence of nitrogen species. The TiN coating was done with the aim of the formation of the duplex layer on the steels surface.

Figure 1: X-ray diffraction patterns of AISI 304 steel (a) untreated and after plasma nitriding at (b) 400°C (c) 450°C and (d) 500°C

Figure 2: X-Ray diffraction of TiN coating performed on the samples nitrided at (a) 400°C (b) 450°C and (c) 500°C

In all steels samples, the diffraction patterns show only the TiN characteristic peak. No peaks of γ -phase or α -phase or CrN phase were detected. It concludes that the formation of TiN is more than the X-ray detection limit. An average crystallite size estimated from the Debye Scherer relation is in the range of 20 nm to 90 nm. The larger TiN particle size was measured for the samples nitrided at 500°C.

The nitride layer was estimated in the range of 25 μm to 80 μm for all the samples. The lowest nitrogen depth is obtained for the sample of 310 steel for all processing temperature because of the highest Cr content in this steel restrict the nitrogen diffusion inside the matrix. The deposition of TiN layer is almost constant for all the samples, i.e., from 200-300 nm. The TEM images of TiN particles deposited on 310 steel shows an average size of 30 nm. This is shown in Fig. 3

Furthermore, the nitrogen diffusion depth of the plasma nitrided samples was analyzed by SEM. Nitrogen diffusion depth is gradually increased with increasing the processing temperature of the steel from 400 to 500°C.

The surface hardness of all untreated steels (AISI 304, 310 and 316 steel) samples has almost constant value of about 1.78 ± 0.10 GPa. The hardness of all nitrided steel specimens was improved after nitriding at 400, 450, and 500°C. Among them, the least hardness of 3.99 GPa is obtained for 304 steel and the highest

hardness of 6.02 GPa is achieved for 316 steel treated at 400°C, as listed in Table 2. Similar behavior is detected in samples nitrided at 450°C and 500°C. Fig. 4 shows the surface hardness of plasma nitrided AISI 304, 310 and 316 austenitic stainless steels treated at 500°C.

Figure 3: Cross section SEM micrographs of plasma nitride at (a) 400°C (b) 450°C (c) TiN layer on (b) and (d) surface morphology of (c)

Figure 5 shows the surface hardness measured on the TiN coated plasma nitrided steel samples. All steel sample nitrided at 500°C shows the maximum hardness after nanocrystalline TiN coating as depicted in Figure 5. The maximum hardness of 13.13 GPa is obtained for the sample of AISI 316 steels are similar to the plasma nitrided at 500°C, and other obtained values are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Surface hardness of untreated, plasma nitrided and TiN coated samples

Hardness (GPa)	Untreated	Plasma nitrided at			TiN coating on plasma nitrided at		
		400°C	450°C	500°C	400°C	450°C	500°C
AISI 304	1.67	3.99	5.44	6.83	6.75	7.79	9.03
AISI 310	1.78	4.76	6.42	7.50	8.81	9.23	10.62
AISI 316	1.88	6.02	7.03	8.42	10.94	11.27	13.13

Figure 4: Surface hardness of the plasma nitrided (a) AISI 304 (b) AISI 310 and (c) AISI 316 stainless steel at 500°C

Figure 5: Surface hardness of TiN coated plasma nitrided (a) AISI 304 (b) AISI 310 and (c) AISI 316 samples at 500°C

The corrosion resistance properties of the steel samples were analyzed by the potentiodynamic curves. The plasma nitrided AISI 304, 310 and 316 stainless steel samples shows better corrosion resistance properties for the nitriding done at 450°C. Corrosion resistance of all steels was enhanced after plasma nitriding in comparison to the untreated steels. The details of the comparison in E_{corr} and I_{corr} values with respect to the plasma nitriding and TiN coating is given in Table 3 and 4.

Figure 6: Corrosion properties of the plasma nitrided (a) AISI 304 (b) AISI 310 and (c) AISI 316 stainless steel at 500°C

The AISI 310 steel sample shows the maximum positive shift in the E_{corr} values in both plasma nitriding at 450°C and TiN coating done on the same sample. The corrosion current density (I_{corr}) of the 316 stainless steel samples is better than the other steels after plasma nitriding and TiN coating as listed in Table 6 and 7. In both cases the plasma nitriding of stainless steel at 450°C shows better results because at this temperature nitrogen is in supersaturated form or in the expanded austenite phase form, which improves the corrosion resistance.

Table 3: Corrosion potential (E_{corr}) after plasma nitriding and TiN coating of steels

E_{corr} (V)	Untreated	Plasma nitrided at			TiN coating on samples plasma nitrided at		
		400°C	450°C	500°C	400°C	450°C	500°C
AISI 304	-0.49	-0.46	-0.33	-0.31	-0.32	-0.29	-0.31
AISI 310	-0.58	-0.51	-0.17	-0.39	-0.88	1.92	0.63
AISI 316	-0.68	-0.53	-0.44	-0.49	-0.32	-0.19	0.34

Figure 7: Corrosion properties of TiN coated plasma nitrided (a) AISI 304 (b) AISI 310 and (c) AISI 316 stainless steel at 500°C

Table 4: Current density (I_{corr}) after plasma nitriding and TiN coating of steels

I_{corr} (μAcm^{-2})	Untreated	Plasma nitrided at			TiN coating on samples plasma nitrided at		
		400°C	450°C	500°C	400°C	450°C	500°C
AISI 304	102	36.3	30.1	25.1	14.1	15.1	17.3
AISI 310	300	62	29	69	2.5	4.6	1.2
AISI 316	30.2	1.48	4.46	5.89	2.38	2.24	2.86

The interfacial contact resistance (ICR) is very important parameter for the bipolar plate's materials having application in the operation of the fuel cells because it measures the current drawn in system when the diffused gas interacts directly with the electrode materials namely bipolar plates.

Generally in operating condition, the compaction force of 150 N/cm^2 is usually considered as an applied force which aroused due to diffusion of gas in fuel cell stacks. Therefore, the ICR between the fuel cell stacks is of foremost importance for operational voltage loss as well as significant reduction in the power density of a cell system. Hence, obtaining a low interfacial contact resistance value is of utmost importance for material used in bipolar plate in fuel cell operating conditions. Figure 8 and 9 portray the ICR value of the 304, 310 and 316 steel samples after plasma nitriding and TiN coating. The 304 samples show the lowest ICR values for all treatment temperatures as given in Table 5. At a particular nitriding temperature of 400°C , all steel samples show the lowest ICR value in the range of 9.9 to $11.12 \text{ m}\Omega\text{cm}^2$, as listed in Table 5. But for the all samples the ICR value is close to the specified US Department of Energy (DOE) target of $10 \text{ m}\Omega\text{cm}^2$. Moreover, after TiN coating no significant change in the ICR is observed.

Figure 8: ICR of the plasma nitrided (a) AISI 304 (b) AISI 310 and (c) AISI 316 stainless steel at 500°C

Figure 9: Corrosion properties of TiN coated plasma nitrided (a) AISI 304 (b) AISI 310 and (c) AISI 316 stainless steel at 500°C

Table 5: ICR of the steel samples after plasma nitriding and TiN coating

ICR ($\text{m}\Omega\text{cm}^2$)	Untreated	Plasma nitrided at			TiN coating on samples plasma nitrided at		
		400°C	450°C	500°C	400°C	450°C	500°C
AISI 304	72.26	9.9	11.5	13.66	8.77	10.32	10.27
AISI 310	89.47	44.69	14.78	29.94	10.92	10.38	11.32
AISI 316	11.65	11.12	12.31	16.53	11.06	11.59	15.49

Conclusions:

On the basis of above comparison, AISI 316 is better than the other studied samples. It is even better than TiN coated samples. Maximum hardness of 13.13 GPa is observed for AISI 316 sample at 500°C . Corrosion resistance is found better in case of AISI 316 samples. However ICR is found better for AISI 304 samples. But all the samples have values in between 8 to $16 \text{ m}\Omega\text{cm}^2$.

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